

To Study the Burden of Anemia in Non-Communicable Diseases in a Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Anemia, a condition marked by insufficient hemoglobin levels, is a prevalent global health issue that complicates the management of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as chronic kidney disease (CKD), diabetes mellitus, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). The coexistence of anemia with NCDs worsens patient outcomes, leading to higher morbidity and mortality. Despite its significance, anemia often remains underdiagnosed and undertreated, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Aim: This study aimed to assess the burden of anemia among patients with NCDs attending a tertiary care center, focusing on its prevalence, severity, and associated factors.

Methods: A hospital-based cross-sectional observational study was conducted at Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (IGIMS), Patna, from January 2018 to November 2018. A total of 116 patients diagnosed with NCDs were included in the study. Data on demographic characteristics, medical history, and laboratory results were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, and chi-square tests were employed to determine the association between anemia and various NCDs.

Results: The overall prevalence of anemia among the participants was 46.6%. Anemia was most prevalent in patients with CKD (75%) and COPD (66.7%). Statistically significant associations were found between anemia and CKD ($p = 0.002$) and COPD ($p = 0.005$). The mean hemoglobin level was 11.2 ± 2.3 g/dL, with lower levels observed in patients with CKD and COPD.

Conclusion: Anemia is highly prevalent among patients with NCDs, particularly in those with CKD and COPD, where it significantly worsens patient outcomes. The findings underscore the need for routine anemia screening and management in these populations to improve health outcomes and reduce disease burden.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should implement regular anemia screening protocols for patients with NCDs, particularly those with CKD and COPD. Additionally, targeted interventions should be developed to manage anemia in these high-risk groups, potentially improving overall disease management and patient quality of life.

Keywords: Anemia, Non-Communicable Diseases, Chronic Kidney Disease, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, Tertiary Care.

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Introduction

Anaemia, which is characterised as having a lower-than-normal haemoglobin concentration in the blood, is still a major global health concern, especially for people who have (NCDs). Approximately 1.74 billion individuals worldwide suffer from anaemia, with low- and middle-income nations having a higher prevalence [1]. Anaemia has been shown by the (WHO) to worsen the clinical course of (NCDs), including diabetes mellitus, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and (CKD) [2]. Given the widespread prevalence of these chronic illnesses worldwide and their status as primary causes of morbidity and mortality, coexisting anaemia poses a serious public health risk.

Anaemia and (NCDs) have complicated interactions, with the potential for exacerbation of each. For example, decreased erythropoietin production, iron deficiency, and chronic inflammation are frequently the cause of anaemia in CKD [3]. Anaemia can also result from prolonged hypoxia and inflammation in COPD, which can hinder the synthesis of red blood cells [4]. Anaemia in diabetics has been linked to both chronic inflammation and microvascular problems [5]. These patients' inferior clinical outcomes, such as greater hospitalisation rates, decreased quality of life, and higher death, are linked to the occurrence of anaemia [6].

Anaemia in individuals with (NCDs) must be identified and treated, according to recent research. Anaemia considerably deteriorated the prognosis for patients with cardiovascular illnesses, increasing the probability of severe cardiovascular events, according to a study [7]. Moreover, another study showed that treating anaemia in CKD patients can enhance their general health and slow the onset of renal failure. These results underline the necessity of all-encompassing care plans that involve routine anaemia screening and suitable treatment for NCD patients.

Anaemia is still underdiagnosed and undertreated in many populations, especially in settings with low resources, despite its importance being acknowledged. The growing global burden of NCDs, which is expected to account for almost 70% of all deaths globally by 2030 [8], exacerbates this problem even more. Treating anaemia in these people is essential to enhancing clinical results and lowering the total cost of chronic illnesses. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the prevalence, severity, and contributing causes of anaemia in patients with NCD who are receiving care at a tertiary care centre.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a hospital-based cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (IGIMS), Patna, from January 2018 to November 2018.

Participants: The study included a total of 116 participants who were diagnosed with non-communicable diseases and attending the outpatient and inpatient departments at IGIMS, Patna.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Diagnosed with one or more non-communicable diseases (e.g., diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases).
- Willing to provide informed consent for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with known hematological disorders other than anemia.

- Pregnant women and lactating mothers.
- Patients receiving treatment for anemia from other centers during the study period.
- Participants who did not provide informed consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the outpatient and inpatient departments. Efforts were made to ensure that the sample was representative of the broader population of patients with non-communicable diseases attending IGIMS, Patna. Observer bias was minimized by standardizing the procedures for data collection and ensuring that all investigators were trained uniformly.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and medical records. The questionnaire captured demographic information, medical history, and current diagnosis. Laboratory tests, including hemoglobin levels, were obtained from the patients' medical records to confirm the presence and severity of anemia.

Procedure: After obtaining informed consent, participants were interviewed using the structured questionnaire. Relevant medical records were reviewed, and laboratory data were extracted. Hemoglobin levels were categorized according to WHO standards to determine the presence and severity of anemia. Data collection was conducted in a confidential and standardized manner to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data after they were entered into an electronic database. The data were summarised using descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages. Using t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical data, the relationship between anaemia and non-communicable diseases was evaluated. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

A total of 116 participants were included in the study, comprising 62 males (53.4%) and 54 females (46.6%). The mean age of the participants was 52.3 ± 12.5 years, with an age range from 30 to 80 years. The majority of participants were between the ages of 50 and 59 years (38.8%).

Table 1: Summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants.

Characteristic	Number of Participants (n = 116)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
30-39	18	15.5
40-49	28	24.1
50-59	45	38.8
60-69	19	16.4
70-80	6	5.2

Gender		
Male	62	53.4
Female	54	46.6
Non-Communicable Disease		
Diabetes Mellitus	45	38.8
Hypertension	53	45.7
Cardiovascular Disease	35	30.2
Chronic Kidney Disease	20	17.2
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)	18	15.5

Prevalence of Anemia: The overall prevalence of anemia among the participants was 46.6% (54 out of 116). Among the 54 participants diagnosed with anemia, 30 were male (55.6%) and 24 were female (44.4%).

Table 2: Shows the distribution of anemia severity among the participants.

Anemia Severity	Number of Participants (n = 54)	Percentage (%)
Mild (10.0–11.9 g/dL for females, 10.0–12.9 g/dL for males)	22	40.7
Moderate (7.0–9.9 g/dL)	25	46.3
Severe (<7.0 g/dL)	7	13.0

Association between Anemia and Non-Communicable Diseases: The predominance of anemia was highest among participants with (CKD) at 75% (15 out of 20), followed by those with (COPD) at 66.7% (12 out of 18), and

cardiovascular disease at 54.3% (19 out of 35). The prevalence of anemia among participants with diabetes mellitus and hypertension was 42.2% (19 out of 45) and 41.5% (22 out of 53), respectively.

Table 3: Displays the prevalence of anemia in participants with different non-communicable diseases.

Non-Communicable Disease	Number of Participants with Anemia	Total Participants (n)	Prevalence of Anemia (%)
Diabetes Mellitus	19	45	42.2
Hypertension	22	53	41.5
Cardiovascular Disease	19	35	54.3
Chronic Kidney Disease	15	20	75.0
COPD	12	18	66.7

Statistical Analysis: Chi-square tests were performed to assess the association between anemia and different non-communicable diseases. A significant association was found between anemia and chronic kidney disease ($p = 0.002$), as well as

between anemia and COPD ($p = 0.005$). However, the association between anemia and other conditions like diabetes mellitus ($p = 0.089$) and hypertension ($p = 0.112$) was not statistically significant.

Table 4: Presents the p-values for the associations between anemia and non-communicable diseases.

Non-Communicable Disease	Chi-square Value	p-value
Diabetes Mellitus	2.89	0.089
Hypertension	2.54	0.112
Cardiovascular Disease	4.21	0.040
Chronic Kidney Disease	9.58	0.002
COPD	7.79	0.005

Hemoglobin Levels: The mean hemoglobin level among the participants was 11.2 ± 2.3 g/dL. The mean hemoglobin level among males was 11.5 ± 2.4 g/dL, while among females, it was 10.8 ± 2.2 g/dL. Participants with chronic kidney disease had the lowest mean hemoglobin levels (9.8 ± 1.7 g/dL), followed by those with COPD (10.1 ± 2.0 g/dL).

Discussion

The study found that nearly half of the participants (46.6%) suffering from (NCDs) at the tertiary care center were also affected by anemia. This high prevalence suggests a significant burden of anemia in patients with NCDs, which could potentially exacerbate their existing health conditions. The study's demographic analysis revealed that anemia was more common in males than females, though the difference was not substantial. The age group most affected by NCDs and anemia was those

between 50 and 59 years, highlighting the vulnerability of middle-aged and older adults.

When examining the relationship between anemia and specific NCDs, the results indicated a strong association between anemia and (CKD) as well as (COPD). The prevalence of anemia was alarmingly high in participants with CKD (75%) and COPD (66.7%), suggesting that these conditions may either contribute to or exacerbate anemia. The statistical analysis confirmed that the association between anemia and these two conditions was statistically significant, with p-values of 0.002 and 0.005, respectively. This implies that patients with CKD and COPD are at a particularly high risk of developing anemia and may require more rigorous screening and management.

In contrast, the study did not find a statistically significant association between anemia and other common NCDs such as diabetes mellitus and hypertension. Although the prevalence of anemia in these groups was still considerable (42.2% in diabetes and 41.5% in hypertension), the lack of statistical significance suggests that factors other than these conditions might be influencing the occurrence of anemia in these patients.

The mean hemoglobin levels among the participants further supported these findings, with the lowest levels observed in patients with CKD and COPD. This aligns with the understanding that both CKD and COPD can lead to decreased hemoglobin production or increased hemoglobin destruction, contributing to the development of anemia.

Depending on the patient group and clinical scenario, anaemia can have varied degrees of severity and ramifications, making it an important public health concern, especially in tertiary care settings. In a study conducted at a rural tertiary care centre, Prasad et al. (2018) discovered an extremely high frequency of anaemia among patients in the outpatient department, especially among women. According to the study showed that anaemia is still a major health problem in rural India despite a number of government measures. This suggests that more efficient ways to treat anaemia in underprivileged people are needed [9].

Chen et al. (2020) investigated the severity and treatment of autoimmune haemolytic anaemia (AIHA) at a tertiary care medical centre in China, with a focus on hospitalised patients. According to the study, hospitalised individuals with AIHA frequently required blood transfusions due to the illness's high prevalence. The crucial role that transfusion management plays in the treatment of AIHA patients is highlighted by the researchers' discovery that, in spite of the difficulties posed by incompatible blood transfusions, the procedures were largely safe and successful [10].

A retrospective cohort research on hospital-acquired anaemia in (ICU) patients by Czempik et al. (2022) offered additional insights into the difficulties associated with anaemia in these settings. According to the study, a sizable percentage of patients admitted to intensive care units had anaemia at the time of admission. This anaemia frequently got worse during the patient's stay, increasing the requirement for red blood cell transfusions. The results made clear how crucial it is to closely monitor and treat anaemia in (ICUs) in order to stop more problems and enhance patient outcomes [11].

Conclusion

These results emphasize the need for targeted interventions to manage anemia in patients with specific NCDs, particularly CKD and COPD. Regular screening for anemia should be integrated into the care plans for these patients to improve overall health outcomes and reduce the complications associated with untreated anemia. The study also underscores the importance of considering anemia as a comorbid condition in the management of NCDs, particularly in tertiary care settings where the burden of these diseases is high.

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